

NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract In the article, it is said that man is born clean and pure like an angel, that he is adapted to live only by striving for goodness and goodness, that he has justice and other noble feelings, and that evil does not exist in his nature or in his spirit, and that evil exists in society, that is, evil comes to man through society. impact, including the positive and negative impact of industrial development on humanity.

Key words: man, spirit, good, bad, industry, society.

INTRODUCTION

If we look at the works of thinkers, we can also see opinions expressed in a unique style. For example, let's quote the following thoughts of Vissarion Grigorievich Belinsky, a famous Russian literary critic and famous sociologist who lived in 1811-1848, who was shorter than the Danish thinker Søren Kierkegaard: "A person is not born bad. On the contrary, man is born conscious and intelligent in the bosom of good things, and he is created to enjoy the happiness of life legitimately. Especially his desire for justice and other feelings are also noble. "Evil is not hidden in a person, but it exists in society." As you can see, in Belinsky's view, the human figure was born as clean and pure as an angel. He adapted to live only in pursuit of goodness and goodness. Has justice and other noble feelings. Evil is not in his nature, nor in his spirit, nor can it be. Evil exists in society¹. So, evil affects a person through society. Simply put, because of society, some people learn evil, and thus start doing evil to themselves and others. Here a question arises.

¹ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). САНОАТ, ФАН-ТЕХНИКА ТАРАҚИЁТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА ИНСОНИЯТ ҲАЁТИ БИЛАН ДИАЛЕКТИК АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 351-358.

Well, if there is no evil in a person, if he is far from evil, then where did evil come from in the society where people live?

MAIN PART

In the process of searching for an answer to the above question, we come to the conclusion that we can agree with some aspects of Belinsky's reasoning above and object to some aspects. What we do agree on is that really young babies are innocent. They cannot do evil, and at the same time they cannot do good. Our objection to Belinsky's conclusion is that if a person is inclined to noble feelings, imbued with goodness, he cannot be affected by the evils of society. If he is under the influence of bad things, it means that he has bad tendencies in his nature. Then society is made up of people. Both the good and the bad in the society were created as a result of people's activities. Because evil is not like a seed of a plant that the wind blows from somewhere. After all, society is not a plowed land, if the seeds of this evil have been planted, grown and spread in one step. The conclusion is that evil exists within the society, in the nature and spirit of the people who make up the society by themselves².

The Russian thinker has another idea about the society and the processes in it, which we cannot but approve one hundred percent. Belinsky writes: "I know that industry is the cause of enormous problems. I also know that industry is a source of countless benefits for the development of society³. It should be admitted that this opinion is a radical outlook on the social relations of its time and has the status of a unique scientific prediction. This is due to the fact that during Belinsky's lifetime, the industry was not very developed and had not yet fully revealed its positive and negative aspects. Especially in the country where the feudal-serf system, Imperial-Samoderjavie monarchical system prevailed, as in Russia, backwardness prevailed.

²Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). САНОАТ, ФАН-ТЕХНИКА ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА ИНСОНИЯТ ҲАЁТИ БИЛАН ДИАЛЕКТИК АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 351-358.

³ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

The development of science and technology was far behind the European countries. Accordingly, the development of the industry was not at a high level. It was a time when all types of industries namely manufacturing industry, transport industry, heavy industry, light industry, mining industry, metallurgical industry etc. were now showing their stature. In such a situation, it was not possible for everyone to make a scientific prediction, as mentioned above. After almost 200 years, we would not be mistaken if we say that Belinsky's argument has been proven 100%. We know that today's booming industry is followed by disasters. First of all, the air we breathe has already lost its purity. We cannot call the water we drink as clear and clean as before. The contents of the delicacies we eat are also full of substances that are harmful to our health. After all, the toxic gases, life-threatening liquid and solid wastes produced by the industry are not disappearing anywhere⁴. They become part of the air we breathe, become clouds, and fall on us in the form of rain and snow. The waste is mixed with the soil and absorbed into the composition of our drinking water. And various agricultural products grown from them are the beauty of our table. As a result, new diseases appear and many people are dying. We also know very well the consequences of accidents in large-scale industrial facilities, in particular, in nuclear power plants. It is difficult to enumerate the number of unpleasant road-transport incidents and the number of people injured as a result of them. Or let's take the case of weapons, one of the industrial products. Millions of people died in the next century due to the use of these weapons. Even now, many people are being killed in conflicts that are happening in different parts of the world and even in countries that are recognized as peaceful. Unfortunately, these weapons are likely to kill many more people in the future. The saddest thing is that humanity has in its hands terrible weapons capable of repeatedly destroying the earth. As if this was not enough, they are trying to improve it further. "However, thinking about the need to stop this kind of development is not nonsense. Because it has

⁴ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). САНОАТ, ФАН-ТЕХНИКА ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА ИНСОНИЯТ ҲАЁТИ БИЛАН ДИАЛЕКТИК АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 351-358.

reached its last level, it is impossible to go further. Although there is no limit to such progress, humanity does not understand it and says to itself: Stop, stop! He does not say that there is no way out of this"⁵. However, instead of coming to their senses, humanity is trying to cover up their actions with various excuses. Apparently, they were forced to create ultra-modern weapons to protect themselves. When asked who, they say the name of the competing countries. For example, by arming the USA, it showed defense against the aggression of the former USSR. Now Russia and China pose a threat to the USA. India points to Pakistan as a source of danger, and Pakistan points to India, and the list goes on and on. But the end of this situation does not lead to good. Metaphorically speaking, this behavior of mankind can be compared to a person sawing a branch of a tree on which he is sitting. One is afraid to think about what terrible consequences it will lead to if the very modern nuclear, chemical, bacteriological and other types of weapons in the hands of the powerful countries of the world are put into action. One thing is certain, there will be no winning side in a war where such weapons are used⁶. Perhaps everyone will be defeated, both those who participated in the war and those who did not. The earth will be turned into a mound, social relations will be destroyed, progress will be pushed back several tens of thousands of years, and mankind will be condemned to start his life again from the primitive community system. If humanity can come out of this war safely. May Allah protect us from such a fate. Just as it is said that God will protect those who protect him, humanity should also strive to change the path of industrial development in a favorable direction. Because industrial development has both positive and negative aspects.

CONCLUSION

⁵Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

⁶ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). САНОАТ, ФАН-ТЕХНИКА ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА ИНСОНИЯТ ҲАЁТИ БИЛАН ДИАЛЕКТИК АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 351-358.

Industry has entered our life and we are used to it. Like it or not, industry has become an integral part of human life. Because now "Railways pass not only through tunnels and bridges, but also under and over walls. The growth of industry and commerce attracts people of all classes and classes, satisfies their demands, and forces them into mutually beneficial and intimate relations. Thus, involuntarily, it eases tensions between people and eliminates unnecessary differences"⁷. Among our contemporaries, who are living with us at this time, there are probably those who do not use industrial products, if we say in a language that you and I understand, technical achievements. For example, everyone has electricity in their homes, we all use our own vehicles or public transportation, every home has a television, a wired or wireless phone, most people have a computer, most people use refrigerators, washing machines, and air conditioners, and the list goes on. can be continued for a long time. This list proves that industrial products, technical samples, as an integral part of our daily life, have already become the essence of human life. To tell the truth, humanity cannot live without them and will not get used to it anymore. As stated above, industry is needed by all people regardless of caste or class. And this industry or technique serves to form a mutually beneficial and reliable relationship between different categories of people. The most important thing is that industry is becoming more and more important in making people's lives easier year by year, improving their supply of material goods, and creating a prosperous way of life.

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⁷ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

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